

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AND ITS EFFECT ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS

Maria Hamdani¹

Scholar, Department of Educational Sciences, National University of Modern Languages, Karachi Campus.
Email: mariahamidani@gmail.com

Saad Muzaffar²

Coordinator / HoD Department of Educational Sciences, National University of Modern Languages, Karachi Campus. Email: saadmuzaffar@numl.edu.pk

ABSTRACT

Attitudes of school personnel towards each other and the students lacking cultural awareness is because of lack of academic achievement. The present study aims to focus on the impact of parental involvement on student's academic performance based on advance scientific knowledge. A quantitative study design was employed by recruiting students aged between 5 years and 16 years. Self-reported questionnaire was used to collect data through mailed survey using google forms. The data gathered via self-administered questionnaire was initially organized on Microsoft excel, which was later coded and uploaded on software Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0. The results showed that majority of the parents monitored their child's homework (65.3%), their time of watching television (77.6%), support in school discipline (98%), strict about school attendance (79.6%), monitor regular attendance (83.7%), contact with the teacher (89.9%), check marks of class test (98%), encourage good academic performance (100%), attend school functions (81.6%), and celebrate academic achievements for motivating children (85.7%). Moreover, more than half of the parents (51%) were aware that the school provides a variety of ways in which they can get involved and volunteer at the school and 67.3% were aware that the school schedules activities and conferences at traditional and nontraditional school hours. The study concluded that involvement of parents in academics of children help to provide the best educational environment for their children.

KEYWORDS: Parental Involvement, Student's Academic Performance, Elementary School Grades, Assessment

INTRODUCTION

Parental involvement is considered as a major aspect in activities that either promote or hinder the success of children since many years. The interaction of parents with their children at home and education setting comprises parental involvement (Jeynes, 2016). There is important recognition of the effect of parental involvement in the academic performance of in certain educational initiative since 2015 like Every Student Succeeds Act (ESSA). This act is considered as the newest authorization of Elementary and Secondary Act (ESEA) receiving re-authorization as No Child Left Behind Act (NCLB) in 2002. The main intention behindhand all these acts was to provide the opportunity to attain high-quality and fair education by the students (Gardner & Mayes, 2013). The topic about significance of involvement of parents in academic performance of children has gained much interest since the earlier phase of 20th century. It was argued that parents and teachers need to work with collaboration to ease the transition of children in kindergarten between 1930s and 1950s. During this period, home and school both were commingled in the mind of children. Improving America's Schools Act (IASA) of 1994 was developed in line with the evolution of an innovative approach to parental involvement (Jeynes, 2016). Substantial and ongoing parental involvement was observed in the IASA of 1994 for enhancing the performance of students (Stephens, 2000).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Previous studies have shown that there is significant impact of parental involvement on student achievement (Wang & Sheikh-Khalil, 2014; Hill, 2015; Camacho-Thompson et al., 2016). Moreover, another study by Benner et al. (2016) recognized parental involvement as an indicator of decreasing rate of high school dropout and increasing academic achievement. Parents are provided opportunities for engaging in school community by the schools through parental involvement programs. All the parents do not get engaged in these programs; although, opportunities for parental involvement are created by school administrators (Williams et al., 2012; Louque & Latunde, 2016). Further, it is suggested that the main reason of lack of understanding is associated with the ways in which parents academically get engaged with their children (Wang & Sheikh-Khalil, 2014). This highlights the need of revisiting the engagement programs at present and make adjustments accordingly for fulfilling the needs of parents. The lack

of academic achievement is contributed by attitudes of school personnel towards each other and the students lacking cultural awareness. Few of the previous studies have also shown convincing empirical research examining parental involvement and academic performance of children (Camacho & Alves, 2017; Roden, 2017). Therefore, the present study aims to provide a correlational analysis of parental involvement and student's academic performance based on advance scientific knowledge.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The study addresses the following research questions;

What is the effect of parental involvement on student's academic performance?

How is the involvement of parents effective on student's academic performance?

How is parental involvement correlated with student's academic performance?

What likely are the main barriers hindering the involvement of parents in their student's learning?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

The research hypothesis of this study are as follows;

Ho: There is statistically no significant relation between involvement of parents and academic performance of students.

H1: There is statistically significant relation between involvement of parents and academic performance of students.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

Parents need to play the role of a teacher in the early years of a child (Kainz & Aikens, 2007). A correlational study by Allen (2017) revealed that there is significant relationship between parental involvement and proficiency of middle school children, specifically in mathematics and reading was statistically significant. It is believed that school administrators are likely to develop strategies for parental involvement based on the relationship between parental involvement and academic performance of students based on the school activities designed for promoting parental engagement. A previous study by Lau and Power (2018) narrated about the importance of using research-based parental involvement strategies across different regional settings, populations, and demographic profiles. The main aim of this quantitative correlational research is to investigate the outcome of parental involvement on children's academic performance at school.

JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

In early 1800s, parents were responsible for the education of their children; however, teachers were later identified as the experts in educating children after the expansion of public education in 1900s. This initiative was supported by most of the American leaders as it was believed that parents are not capable enough to provide necessary skills to their children. However, in the recent time, organizations like Parents for Public Schools are advocating for the incorporation of stronger language that pertains to involvement of parents. This has mandated school districts towards the creation of policies for parental involvement in enhancing student performances.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Several activities are included in involvement of parent to enhance student performance in home setting through providing assistance in homework, discussing about school, and reading with/to the children. It is believed that students are likely to have higher grades, increased test scores, and increased capability of enrolling in challenging programs with the help of parental involvement. This study is significant as involvement of parent is an important part of student achievement in middle school. This study is likely to provide better understanding about the significance of parental involvement in the academic performance of students.

DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

Some of the myths among teachers that are likely to affect the academic performance of students include; parents do not value education, lack of appropriate intellectual experiences, lack of motivation to learn, and lack of parental involvement. According to Simon and Goes (2013), the boundaries specified for the study are termed as delimitation of the study. The delimitations usually arise while developing the study plan, based on the conscious exclusionary and inclusionary decisions. It includes the choices made by the researcher that need to be mentioned, beforehand. They result from the specialized choices made by the researcher about the variables, research questions, use of study paradigm, choice of participants, and the theoretical framework. The major limitation of this study is that it has mainly focused on the perspectives of parents from a specific region. This is likely to increase the difficulty of transferring the study results to diverse ethnic groups. The study lacks to understand the associated ways, in which parents are likely to get engaged with their children, academically. This can be encountered by focusing on the current engagement programs and making appropriate adjustments for the parents to perform their duties.

BASIC ASSUMPTIONS IN THE STUDY

The study has included factors, which are not under control of the researcher; however, the relevance of the study will be decreased without considering those factors. It is believed that existence of research problem alone is not possible without basic assumptions (Leedy & Ormrod, 2010). It cannot be stated that these assumptions are made, rather than just justifying the assumptions to be true. For instance, it is assumed that parental involvement would still be an issue at middle school to complete the study on parental involvement. Moreover, it is also assumed that parents are likely to respond truthfully while conducting interviews with parents.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE**PARENTAL PERCEPTIONS ON INVOLVEMENT IN RELATIONS TO STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE**

Active involvement of parents is responsible for facilitating the learning and engagement of children in school by sustaining their learning interests, rather than just increasing awareness among students about parental expectations for schooling (Wong et al., 2018). One of the previous studies by Wang and Sheikh-Khalil (2014) provided evidence about the impact of parental involvement on the educational outcomes of students considering the effect of school engagement. It is possible to improve the affective states of students like increase in positive feelings leading to better academic outcomes through active participation of students in class and extra-curricular activities (Voelkl, 2012). However, this can only be achieved if students start experiencing intrinsic enjoyment in school work (Bempechat & Shernoff 2012). There is well-establishment of positive perceptions of parental involvement in the educational achievements of students; however, at time overparenting can have significant adverse effects on the children. Further investigation is warranted based on the excessive parental involvement that hinders the academic, as well as psychosocial development of the children. One of the recent studies by Wong et al. (2018) examined the relationship of educational involvement of parents at home and school with the impact on children's academic performance and psychological health. The results revealed that there is positive association of home-based educational involvement of parents with the psychosocial well-being and language competence of the children based in the engagement of children with school. There is indirect effect of school-based parental involvement on the prosocial behavior of students via school engagement.

PARENTAL ROLE OF INVOLVEMENT AND STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

Some of the previous meta-analysis studies have reported statistically significant association of parental involvement and academic achievement of students (Jeynes, 2007; Hill & Tyson, 2009; Boonk et al., 2018). For instance, a previous study by Hill and Tyson (2009) provided summary of around fifty studies and stated that there are two types of involvements that is linked with performance of students. The two type's involvements are parental involvement and academic socialization. However, the same study showed insignificant relation of academic performance with involvement of parents at home. The motivation level of children is likely to increase as parents start supporting the development of children's independence, along with reducing their involvement at home. It is believed that this happens as the children become more responsible towards their actions and academic performance (Froiland et al., 2015),

ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

Considering academic achievement, a previous meta-analysis study by Castro et al. (2015) stated some types of parental involvement having significant impact of the academic performance of students such as conducting regular conversation about classes and other activities, high academic expectations, and encouraging reading habits. However, another study by Rogers et al. (2009) stated that some patterns of parental involvement like monitoring school attendance and checking homework have no impact on the performance of children, rather it might pose negative impact. Such as, it can be expected that constant monitoring from the parents would increase pressure on the students, resulting in demotivation among them (Rogers et al., 2009). Parental involvement in educational setting is considered as a mechanism of increasing the success of students in school. This is likely to decrease the significant gap in educational outcomes. For instance, there is beneficial effect of encouragement, increased expectations, and learning environment on the academic achievements of studies, regardless of their national, economic, social, and cultural backgrounds (Goshin & Mertsalova, 2018). Some of the previous studies conducted in different countries across the world have shown that there is positive effect of parental involvement on the performance, as well as personal development of students (Su & Reeve, 2011; Froiland et al., 2015). Further, it is also stated that support received by the students from their parents is significantly associated with the autonomy, academic achievement, and motivation to learn among the students (Su & Reeve, 2011; Froiland et al., 2015). One of the previous studies by Prakhov et al. (2020) also confirmed the significant impact of parental involvement on the selection of educational path.

TEACHER INTERACTIONS

Human interplay capable of developing communication and interaction between the student and the teacher is defined as teacher student relationship (Krane & Klevan, 2019). The emotional development and psychological progress of a child depends on the relationship between the student and the teacher. This is because teachers are present in everyday life of the students (Pianta & Allen, 2008). Positive peer relation is facilitated and well-being of student is promoted as the result of positive teacher and student relationship (Wallace & Chhuon. 2014). A recent study by Krane et al. (2016) stated that teacher student relationship and mental health of the students are associated. The factors that affect development of teacher student relationship include certain contextual factors, along with individual, human qualities, and emotional factors. The contextual factors, basically, includes interaction of multi-level system in a complex interplay (Sabol & Pianta, 2012). Interaction between multi-level system considering the school environment, class organization, and relationship between an individual teacher and student majorly define the development of teacher student relationship. Parents are considered among the essential microsystems contributing to the development of teacher student relationship based on the development system theory. Teacher and student relationships are significantly affected based on the collaboration of school with the parents.

PARENTAL PARTICIPATION

An essential role is played by family in the experience of students at school. Previous studies have shown that there is significant effect of structural and dynamic factors on the academic performance of students based on the involvement or support of parents in education (Sarrato, 2012; Serna & Martínez, 2019). Here, the structural factors include cultural resources, educational and socio-economic level of parents, and family structure. While, the dynamic factors include affective climate, level of cognition among parent, relationship between child and parent, and disciplinary style. These factors correspond to the concerns in parental behavior and their participation at school and home to help their children with school learning experiences. There might be either direct or indirect impact of parental involvement on the academic achievement of students (Jeynes, 2016). The positive perceptions of children about school mediates their improvement in academic performance. Academic achievement of students is notes based on their level of satisfaction, self-esteem, prosocial behavior, academic motivation, school commitment, social competence, and normative adjustments (Mounts et al., 2006). However, the effectiveness of parental involvement on either good or bad academic achievement has not been proved; although, parental involvement is linked with the school adjustment in different studies.

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AND ITS INDIRECT EFFECTS

There is positive association of the attitude and motivation among children with parental involvement (Simpkins et al., 2015; Hill & Wang 2015; Frostick et al. 2016). For instance, Simpkins et al. (2015) stated that the value placed by adolescents on different subjects can be predicted positively through involvement of patents in scientific subjects. Another study conducted by Hill and Wang (2015) narrated that educational aspiration is positively associated with monitoring that includes maintaining knowledge related to youth activities. Few of the previous studies have also highlighted about positive prediction of academic achievement among the students based on their attitude towards a subject, domain-specific values, educational aspiration, enjoyment, and intrinsic motivation (Lipnevich et al. 2016; García et al. 2016; Jung & Zhang 2016). It has been shown that mathematics achievement among the children of elementary schools can be predicted through the enjoyment of mathematics. Some of the studies have also shown indirect association between academic achievement and involvement of parents based on the behaviors, aspirations, and motivational resources of the students. One of the previous studies stated that there is positive association of parental involvement on GPA because of enhanced educational engagement. A previous study by Jung and Zhang (2016) narrated that educational aspirations pose indirect but positive effects of parents' involvement on the academic achievement of students. These studies have failed to show the perception of students about the involvement of parents considering their senses of efficacy, different cognitive developments, and need of direct parental involvement. It is believed that there is difference in the association between involvement of parents and students' achievements at different levels in school. The above-mentioned discussion clearly depicts about the indirect involvement of parents in the academic achievement of children based on their attitudes.

BENEFITS TO SCHOOL

The need of parents to work with schools and get involved in children learning has been adopted by most of the school leaders, policy makers, and teachers. Parental involvement can be observed in form of enhanced communication, contribution to student achievement, and alleviation of student disciplinary problem for supporting the rigorous demands of school curriculum (Carpenter et al., 2016). Previous studies have focused on motivation of parent involvement in their child's education by extensive researching and investigating the relationship between student achievement and parental involvement (Hill & Tyson, 2009; Wilder, 2014; Castro et al., 2015). The focus of

previous studies was on the examination of different levels and patterns of parental involvement based on the socio-economic background (Wang et al., 2016; Malone, 2017). It is believed that parents belonging to lower socio-economic backgrounds are likely to fail in playing their adequate role for academic achievements of their children, in comparison to the advantaged social milieu (Wang et al., 2016; Malone, 2017). The school leaders, policy makers, and teachers need to do more for facilitating the extent of parent's involvement from lower socio-economic backgrounds.

COMMUNICATION BETWEEN TEACHERS AND PARENTS AND STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

Children are likely to learn and adopt things from the expression of emotions and use of learned reactions from their parents, considering the parent child interactions for handling their issues. Children adopt skills of managing emotions by observing behavior of their parents resulting in the development of prosocial behaviors and social relationships (Wong et al., 2018). In order to prevent misbehavior at home and school, there is need to have adequate emotional control. Understanding of parents about the performance of students at school can be increased through school-based involvement. This can be done by attending school events, communicating with children, and understanding the performance of children at school. One of the previous studies by Pomerantz et al. (2007) stated that communication between parent and child about school issues are associated with increased supportive family interactions and decreased learning distress at home. Moreover, positive relationship between parents and children help in fostering the vocabulary and cognitive development of children (Rodriguez & Tamis-LeMonda, 2011).

THEORETICAL GROUNDING

There is existence of certain differences in literature that is realized after going through empirical studies closely. This is because majority of the studies have been conducted, without wide acceptance of their theoretical framework. The unclarity about parental involvement is because this concept has been operationalized, measured, and implemented in many ways, which has diminished its actual meaning. These problems have arisen due to complex concept and confusion because of absenteeism of a clear definition. Therefore, the present study aims to focus on the outcome of parental involvement on academic performance of children.

METHODOLOGY

The aim of present study was to determine the extent of parental involvement required for enhancing the achievement and academic level of students. A quantitative study design was employed to assess the effect of parental involvement on the performance of students in school. This study is likely to render the possible existing association of involvement of parents and academic performance of students of ages ranging between 5 years and 16 years. The main concern of descriptive research design is towards providing description and explanation of events in which the participants were, they are, or they could be (McMillan & Schumacher, 2010). The detailed description of characteristics of involvement of parents in the academic performance of their children can be achieved by employing case study design. This type of research design requires collection of in-depth information from the study participants. It also involves analyzing the collected information to know about the effect of involvement of parents in the academic achievement of their children.

TARGET POPULATION

The total number of participants that are of interest to the researcher is termed as target population. In the present study, the target population includes students and parents of different primary and secondary school. The involvement of study participants was because they were likely to provide data based on their views and experience regarding academic performance of students. Purposive sampling method was employed in this study for getting in-depth understanding about the effect of parental involvement on the academic performance of students. The selection criteria set for this study is; academic performance indicators >650, increased population of socioeconomically disadvantaged students, and use of traditional parenting program.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

The characteristic of target population is represented through a sample of small group of people. The size of an appropriate sample cannot be determined through fixed number or percentage, rather it relies on the nature of population that is of interest and targeted for data collection and analysis (Guest et al., 2017). The nature of the study allowed using purposive sampling method for recruiting students and parents, who would provide relevant information to researcher. Participation from private schools was favored along with students from both the genders were included in the study sample.

INSTRUMENT DEVELOPMENT

The instrument used for data collection in this study includes close ended questionnaire. Previous literature was deeply reviewed for designing of the study instrument. The demographic information of students included their

gender, age, and class. Whereas, demographic information of parents included their gender and occupation. The questions assessing effect of parental involvement on academic performance of students was assessed based on close ended questions with three options; Yes, No and Sometimes. This survey helped in the identification of effectiveness of involvement of parents on the level of achievement of their children.

PLAN OF DATA COLLECTION

The students and parents were administered the self-report questionnaire through email. The researcher was not able to collect information in hand because of COVID-19 pandemic. Therefore, data was collected through mailed survey using Google forms. The total time needed for filling the questionnaire would be around 5-6 minutes. The questionnaire nowhere asked about the names of students and parents to maintain their confidentiality. Adequate participation in this study was ensured through multiple notification /messages on whatsapp and facebook messenger.

DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

The validity and reliability of study instrument was ensured via process of data collection and findings analysis by the researcher. Pilot study and peer review was conducted in this study for ensuring the questionnaire’s validity. The data gathered via self-administered questionnaire was initially organized on Microsoft excel. The data was then coded and uploaded on software Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0 to analyze the data and find the effect of involvement of parents on the enhancement of student performance at school.

DATA ANALYSIS

RESULTS

Figures 1-5 represents the demographic profile of the students and parents. The results depict that majority of the students (77.6%) were females and 46.9% were aged between 9 to 12 years. Majority of the students that is 44.9% and 40.8% were studying in class 1-4 and 5-8, respectively. Concerning the demographic profile of the parents, the results showed that 95.9% of the parents, who gave responses were mothers. Moreover, 65.3% of them were neither having formal nor personal employment.

Figure 1: Gender of students

Figure 2: Age of students

Figure 3: Class of students

Figure 4: Which parent?

Figure 5: Occupation of the parent

The responses of students towards involvement of their parents in their academics have been presented in table 1. Majority of the students stated that their parents monitored their homework (65.3%), monitored their time of watching television (77.6%), support in school discipline (98%), strict about school attendance (79.6%), monitor regular attendance (83.7%), contact with the teacher (89.9%), check marks of class test (98%), encourage good academic performance (100%), attend school functions (81.6%), and celebrate academic achievements for motivating children (85.7%).

Table 1: Responses of Students towards parent’s involvement in their academics

Question	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Do your parents advise you in your homework activities?	Yes	39	79.6
	No	2	4.1
	Sometimes	8	16.3
Do your parents monitor you while doing homework?	Yes	32	65.3
	No	3	6.1
	Sometimes	14	28.6
Do your parents help you while you do your homework?	Yes	20	40.8
	No	4	8.2
	Sometimes	25	51
Do your parents keep track of your television viewing habit?	Yes	38	77.6
	No	4	8.2
	Sometimes	7	14.3
Do your parents support you in following school discipline?	Yes	48	98
	No	1	2
	Sometimes	-	-
Do your parents show strictness regarding your sleep time?	Yes	33	67.3
	No	3	6.1
	Sometimes	13	26.5
Do your parents help you in assignments completion?	Yes	26	53.1
	No	4	8.2
	Sometimes	19	38.8
Do you go for private tuitions arranged by your parents?	Yes	13	26.5
	No	35	71.4
	Sometimes	1	2
Are your parents strict about you being regular to school?	Yes	39	79.6
	No	3	6.1
	Sometimes	7	14.3
Are your parents keeping track of your regular attendance?	Yes	41	83.7
	No	2	4.1
	Sometimes	6	12.2
Do your parents involve your teacher for checking attendance?	Yes	16	32.7
	No	28	57.1
	Sometimes	5	10.2
Do your parents aware about your teachers’ method of teaching?	Yes	34	69.4
	No	5	10.2
	Sometimes	10	20.4
Are your parents in touch with your teacher?	Yes	44	89.9
	No	1	2
	Sometimes	4	8.2
Do your parents keep in touch with your teachers to inquire about your progress in studies?	Yes	37	75.5
	No	7	14.3
	Sometimes	5	10.2
Do your parents keep a check of your marks in class tests?	Yes	48	98
	No	-	-
	Sometimes	1	2
Do your parents discuss with your teachers if your homework is not done?	Yes	24	49
	No	18	36.7
	Sometimes	7	14.3
Do your parents encourage you to get good marks or	Yes	49	100
	No	-	-

perform well in academics?	Sometimes	-	-
Are your parents present at your school functions?	Yes	40	81.6
	No	2	4
	Sometimes	7	14.3
Do your parents motivate you to read books or use the library?	Yes	32	65.3
	No	3	6.1
	Sometimes	14	28.6
Are your parents always celebrating your good academic performance to keep you motivated?	Yes	42	85.7
	No	3	6.1
	Sometimes	4	8.2

Figure 6 has presented responses of parents towards their involvement in academic performance of their children. The results show that more than half of them (51%) were aware that the school provides a variety of ways in which they can get involved and volunteer at the school. Around 67.3% were aware that the school schedules activities and conferences at traditional and nontraditional school hours and 61.2% reported that school provides a Parent Resource Center to access resources for their children.

Figure 6: Responses of Parents towards their involvement in their children’s academics

DISCUSSION

MAJOR FINDINGS

The present study focusing on the impact of parental involvement on the academic performance of students clearly showed that involvement of parents in academics of children help to provide the best education environment for their children. The results clearly depict that there is significant effect of involvement of parents on academic performance of students. The results also exhibited significant positive association between involvement of parents and student performance at school. Majority of the parents were involved in their child’s daily activities such as monitoring their time of watching television, regular attendance at school, encouragement in academic performance, and regular presence at the school functions. This shows that involvement of parents helps also needs to focus on creating conducive home environments for studying and motivating, along with setting realistic expectations enhances performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of this study clearly recommend that a leading role is taken by the parents to support the educational endeavors of their children because they are among the first educators, who are responsible for exposing them to

academic world. Students can excel in their academics based on the strong relationship between the teacher and parent. Realistic expectations need to be set by the parents regarding their children performance and then motivate their children for achieving it. The confidence that parents show in their children help in building high level of confidence among their children and those children are more likely to succeed in their academic studies. In the similar context, policy makers also need to play an important role in this case by instructing the teachers about parental involvement, along with encouraging the parents to get involved in academic performance of their children.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that majority of the parents were highly involved in academics of their children as they believe that education is the only way to go ahead. The children receive advices from their parents about studying according to the timetable and follow the instructions provided in the class. According to majority of the students, their parents felt proud on their good grade and celebrate on their children's success. An important role is played by parents in helping their children to develop good study habit. Lastly, it is recommended that future studies should focus on the impact of socio-economic status of parents and parent teacher interaction on the academic performance of students.

REFERENCES

- Allen, C. S. (2017). *Parental involvement and academic achievement of middle school African American students in southeast Arkansas* (Doctoral dissertation, Grand Canyon University).
- Bempechat, J., & Shernoff, D. J. (2012). Parental influences on achievement motivation and student engagement. In *Handbook of research on student engagement* (pp. 315-342). Springer, Boston, MA.
- Benner, A. D., Boyle, A. E., & Sadler, S. (2016). Parental involvement and adolescents' educational success: The roles of prior achievement and socioeconomic status. *Journal of youth and adolescence, 45*(6), 1053-1064.
- Boonk, L., Gijsselaers, H. J., Ritzen, H., & Brand-Gruwel, S. (2018). A review of the relationship between parental involvement indicators and academic achievement. *Educational Research Review, 24*, 10-30.
- Camacho, A., & Alves, R. A. (2017). Fostering parental involvement in writing: development and testing of the program Cultivating Writing. *Reading and Writing, 30*(2), 253-277.
- Camacho-Thompson, D. E., Gillen-O'Neel, C., Gonzales, N. A., & Fuligni, A. J. (2016). Financial strain, major family life events, and parental academic involvement during adolescence. *Journal of youth and adolescence, 45*(6), 1065-1074.
- Carpenter, B. W., Young, M. D., Bowers, A., & Sanders, K. (2016). Family involvement at the secondary level: Learning from Texas Borderland Schools. *NASSP Bulletin, 100*(1), 47-70.
- Castro, M., Expósito-Casas, E., López-Martín, E., Lizasoain, L., Navarro-Asencio, E., & Gaviria, J. L. (2015). Parental involvement on student academic achievement: A meta-analysis. *Educational research review, 14*, 33-46.
- Chhuon, V., & Wallace, T. L. (2014). Creating connectedness through being known: Fulfilling the need to belong in US high schools. *Youth & Society, 46*(3), 379-401.
- Christenson, S. L., Reschly, A. L., & Wylie, C. (Eds.). (2012). *Handbook of research on student engagement*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Froiland, J. M., Mayor, P., & Herlevi, M. (2015). Motives emanating from personality associated with achievement in a Finnish senior high school: Physical activity, curiosity, and family motives. *School Psychology International, 36*(2), 207-221.
- Frostick, C., Phillips, G., Renton, A., & Moore, D. (2016). The educational and employment aspirations of adolescents from areas of high deprivation in London. *Journal of youth and adolescence, 45*(6), 1126-1140.
- García, T., Rodríguez, C., Betts, L., Areces, D., & González-Castro, P. (2016). How affective-motivational variables and approaches to learning predict mathematics achievement in upper elementary levels. *Learning and Individual Differences, 49*, 25-31.
- Gardner III, R., & Mayes, R. D. (2013). African american learners. *Preventing School Failure: Alternative Education for Children and Youth, 57*(1), 22-29.
- Goshin, M., & Mertsalova, T. (2018). Types of parental involvement in education, socio-economic status of the family and students' academic results. *Вопросы образования, 3* (eng).
- Guest, G., Namey, E., & McKenna, K. (2017). How many focus groups are enough? Building an evidence base for nonprobability sample sizes. *Field methods, 29*(1), 3-22.
- Hill, N. E. (2015). Including fathers in the picture: A meta-analysis of parental involvement and students' academic achievement. *Journal of Educational Psychology, 107*(4), 919.
- Hill, N. E., & Tyson, D. F. (2009). Parental involvement in middle school: a meta-analytic assessment of the strategies that promote achievement. *Developmental psychology, 45*(3), 740.

- Hill, N. E., & Wang, M. T. (2015). From middle school to college: Developing aspirations, promoting engagement, and indirect pathways from parenting to post high school enrollment. *Developmental psychology, 51*(2), 224.
- Jeynes, W. H. (2007). The relationship between parental involvement and urban secondary school student academic achievement: A meta-analysis. *Urban education, 42*(1), 82-110.
- Jeynes, W. H. (2016). A meta-analysis: The relationship between parental involvement and African American school outcomes. *Journal of Black Studies, 47*(3), 195-216.
- Jung, E., & Zhang, Y. (2016). Parental involvement, children's aspirations, and achievement in new immigrant families. *The Journal of Educational Research, 109*(4), 333-350.
- Kainz, K., & Aikens, N. L. (2007). Governing the family through education: A genealogy on the home/school relation. *Equity & Excellence in Education, 40*(4), 301-310.
- Krane, V., & Klevan, T. (2019). There are three of us: parents' experiences of the importance of teacher-student relationships and parental involvement in upper secondary school. *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth, 24*(1), 74-84.
- Krane, V., Karlsson, B., Ness, O., & Kim, H. S. (2016). Teacher-student relationship, student mental health, and dropout from upper secondary school: A literature review.
- Latunde, Y., & Clark-Louque, A. (2016). Untapped resources: Black parent engagement that contributes to learning. *The Journal of Negro Education, 85*(1), 72-81.
- Lau, E. Y. H., & Power, T. G. (2018). Parental involvement during the transition to primary school: Examining bidirectional relations with school adjustment. *Children and Youth Services Review, 88*, 257-266.
- Leedy, P. D., & Ormrod, J. (2010). E. 2010. Practical research: Planning and design. *Ohio, Merrill Prentice Hall*.
- Lipnevich, A. A., Preckel, F., & Krumm, S. (2016). Mathematics attitudes and their unique contribution to achievement: Going over and above cognitive ability and personality. *Learning and Individual Differences, 47*, 70-79.
- Malone, D. (2017). Socioeconomic Status: A Potential Challenge for Parental Involvement in Schools. *Delta Kappa Gamma Bulletin, 83*(3).
- McMillan, J. H., & Schumacher, S. (2010). Research in Education: Evidence-Based Inquiry, MyEducationLab Series. *Pearson*.
- Mounts, N. S., Valentiner, D. P., Anderson, K. L., & Boswell, M. K. (2006). Shyness, sociability, and parental support for the college transition: Relation to adolescents' adjustment. *Journal of youth and adolescence, 35*(1), 68-77.
- Pianta, R. C., & Allen, J. P. (2008). Building capacity for positive youth development in secondary school classrooms: Changing teachers' interactions with students.
- Pomerantz, E. M., Moorman, E. A., & Litwack, S. D. (2007). The how, whom, and why of parents' involvement in children's academic lives: More is not always better. *Review of educational research, 77*(3), 373-410.
- Prakhov, I., Kotomina, O., & Sazhina, A. (2020). Parental involvement and the educational trajectories of youth in Russia. *International Journal of Educational Development, 78*, 102252.
- Rhoden, S. (2017). "Trust Me, You Are Going to College": How Trust Influences Academic Achievement in Black Males. *The Journal of Negro Education, 86*(1), 52-64.
- Rodriguez, E. T., & Tamis-LeMonda, C. S. (2011). Trajectories of the home learning environment across the first 5 years: Associations with children's vocabulary and literacy skills at prekindergarten. *Child development, 82*(4), 1058-1075.
- Rogers, M. A., Theule, J., Ryan, B. A., Adams, G. R., & Keating, L. (2009). Parental involvement and children's school achievement: Evidence for mediating processes. *Canadian Journal of School Psychology, 24*(1), 34-57.
- Sabol, T. J., & Pianta, R. C. (2012). Recent trends in research on teacher-child relationships. *Attachment & human development, 14*(3), 213-231.
- Sarrato, CS (2012). *Psychosocial factors in the risk of school failure: the social context in academic performance* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Castilla-La Mancha).
- Serna, C., & Martínez, I. (2019). Parental Involvement as a Protective Factor in School Adjustment among Retained and Promoted Secondary Students. *Sustainability, 11*(24), 7080.
- Simon, M. K., & Goes, J. (2013). Assumptions, limitations, delimitations, and scope of the study. Retrieved from *dissertationrecipes.com*.
- Simpkins, S. D., Price, C. D., & Garcia, K. (2015). Parental support and high school students' motivation in biology,

- chemistry, and physics: Understanding differences among latino and caucasian boys and girls. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 52(10), 1386-1407.
- Stephens, R. D. (2000). *From the courthouse to the schoolhouse: Making successful transitions*. US Department of Justice, Office of Justice Programs, Office of Juvenile Justice and Delinquency Prevention.
- Su, Y. L., & Reeve, J. (2011). A meta-analysis of the effectiveness of intervention programs designed to support autonomy. *Educational psychology review*, 23(1), 159-188.
- Wang, M. T., & Sheikh-Khalil, S. (2014). Does parental involvement matter for student achievement and mental health in high school?. *Child development*, 85(2), 610-625.
- Wang, Y., Deng, C., & Yang, X. (2016). Family economic status and parental involvement: Influences of parental expectation and perceived barriers. *School Psychology International*, 37(5), 536-553.
- Wilder, S. (2014). Effects of parental involvement on academic achievement: A meta-synthesis. *Educational Review*, 66(3), 377-397.
- Williams, T. T., & Sánchez, B. (2012). Parental involvement (and uninvolvement) at an inner-city high school. *Urban Education*, 47(3), 625-652.
- Wong, R. S. M., Ho, F. K. W., Wong, W. H. S., Tung, K. T. S., Chow, C. B., Rao, N., ... & Ip, P. (2018). Parental involvement in primary school education: Its relationship with children's academic performance and psychosocial competence through engaging children with school. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 27(5), 1544-1555.